

Clinicohematological and Biochemical Profile of Anemia in Pediatric Age Group

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Abstract:

This study at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital focused on analysing the clinicohematological and biochemical profiles of anaemia in 100 paediatric patients through a cross-sectional observational approach. The study revealed a considerable number of individuals with microcytic anaemia (60%), primarily due to insufficient iron levels. Additionally, it detected notable cases of macrocytic anaemia linked to deficiencies in vitamin B12 and folate. The findings emphasise the importance of customised screening and intervention strategies to effectively tackle the various types and causes of anaemia in children. These initiatives are crucial in enhancing the health outcomes of children and promoting their optimal growth and development.

Keywords: Pediatric Anemia, Microcytic Anemia, Iron Deficiency, Vitamin B12 Deficiency

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Introduction

Anaemia continues to be a widespread concern in children globally, greatly affecting their growth, development, and overall well-being [1]. This condition, which involves a lack of red blood cells or haemoglobin, can be caused by different factors that depend on a person's age, diet, and existing medical conditions [2]. Accurate diagnosis and targeted therapeutic interventions are essential when profiling anaemia in paediatric patients, taking into account clinicohematological and biochemical factors [3]. Medical professionals often evaluate haematological parameters to classify anaemia into microcytic, normocytic, and macrocytic types [4]. These types can provide valuable insights into the various underlying causes of anaemia. Additional biochemical tests can provide valuable insights into identifying specific deficiencies or disorders, including iron deficiency, vitamin B12 levels, or markers of inflammation [5,6].

This introduction provides an overview of the clinicohematological and biochemical profile of anaemia in children, highlighting the importance of thorough diagnostic assessments. This discussion will emphasise the significance of taking a detailed approach to managing paediatric anaemia. By examining the connections between clinical features and laboratory findings, the goal is to

improve patient outcomes through personalised treatment strategies.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational analysis conducted over one year to evaluate the clinicohematological and biochemical profiles of anemia in pediatric patients.

Study Setting: The research was carried out at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (DMCH), Darbhanga, a tertiary care center catering to a diverse pediatric population.

Participants:

A total of 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia were enrolled in the study. Inclusion criteria were:

- Patients aged from 1 month to 18 years.
- Diagnosed with anemia based on hemoglobin levels below the age-specific normal range as per WHO guidelines.

Exclusion criteria included:

- Patients with chronic diseases affecting hemoglobin levels, such as chronic kidney disease or malignancies.
- Patients receiving treatment for anemia prior to the study period.

Data Collection

Data was collected through a structured proforma which included:

- Demographic details (age, sex, dietary habits).
- Medical history and clinical examination findings.
- Laboratory investigations including complete blood count (CBC), serum iron levels, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), ferritin, vitamin B12, and folate levels.

Hematological Assessments

Blood samples were collected using standard phlebotomy techniques. Hemoglobin concentration, MCV, and RDW were measured using an automated hematology analyzer. Classification of anemia was done based on the WHO criteria:

- Microcytic anemia (MCV < 80 fL)
- Normocytic anemia (MCV 80-100 fL)
- Macrocytic anemia (MCV > 100 fL)

Biochemical Tests: Biochemical assessments were performed to determine the underlying causes of anemia. Serum iron, TIBC, and ferritin were measured by colorimetric methods. Vitamin B12 and folate levels were determined using immunoassay techniques.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using statistical software SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. The prevalence of different types of anemia and associated biochemical abnormalities were calculated. Chi-square tests were used for categorical data, and ANOVA was employed for continuous variables to identify significant differences. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 100 paediatric patients diagnosed with anaemia were included in the study, with an equal

distribution of 52% males and 48% females. Here is the breakdown of the age distribution: 30% fell within the age range of 1 month to 2 years, while 45% were aged between 3 to 10 years. The remaining 25% consisted of adolescents aged 11 to 18 years. Upon analysis, it was found that a majority of the participants exhibited microcytic anaemia, with a significant portion also experiencing normocytic and macrocytic anaemia. The age group of 3 to 10 years showed a higher prevalence of microcytic anaemia. The average haemoglobin level among the participants in the study was determined to be 9.8 g/dL. Individuals diagnosed with microcytic anaemia exhibited the lowest average haemoglobin levels at 8.5 g/dL. This was followed by patients with normocytic anaemia at 10.6 g/dL, and those with macrocytic anaemia at 11.2 g/dL. In cases of microcytic anaemia, the average MCV was 74 fL, while in normocytic anaemia it was 88 fL, and in macrocytic anaemia it was 104 fL.

The most prevalent cause of anaemia, discovered in 70% of cases with microcytic anaemia, was a deficiency in iron. In these patients, the average serum iron level was 30 µg/dL, which fell below the normal paediatric range. The levels of ferritin showed a decrease, averaging at 15 ng/mL. On the other hand, macrocytic anaemia was found to be mainly caused by deficiencies in vitamin B12 and folate, impacting a significant 80% of patients in this particular group. The statistical analysis revealed a noteworthy correlation between the type of anaemia and age group ($p < 0.01$). It was observed that microcytic anaemia was more commonly found in younger children. The relationship between low iron levels and the presence of microcytic anaemia showed a strong statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). This study highlights the significant occurrence of microcytic anaemia in paediatric patients, mainly caused by a lack of iron. It is recommended to regularly screen children for anaemia, with a specific emphasis on monitoring their diet and managing micronutrient intake to effectively address this condition.

Parameter	Overall (n=100)	Microcytic Anemia (n=60)	Normocytic Anemia (n=25)	Macrocytic Anemia (n=15)
Gender Distribution				
Male	52%	55%	48%	47%
Female	48%	45%	52%	53%
Age Group				
1 month - 2 years	30%	35%	20%	20%
3 years - 10 years	45%	50%	40%	33%
11 years - 18 years	25%	15%	40%	47%
Mean Hemoglobin (g/dL)	9.8	8.5	10.6	11.2
Mean MCV (fL)	85	74	88	104
Biochemical Profiles				
Iron Deficiency	70% (of microcytic)	100%	20%	0%
Vitamin B12 Deficiency	12%	0%	10%	80%
Folate Deficiency	10%	0%	5%	80%

The concept of statistical significance

- Significant correlation found between age and anaemia type ($p < 0.01$).
- Strong association observed between iron levels and microcytic anaemia ($p < 0.001$).

This table presents an overview of the study's outcomes, including information on the demographic distribution, haematological and biochemical profiles, and statistical analysis results.

Discussion

This study effectively analysed the clinicohematological and biochemical profiles of paediatric anaemia within a diverse sample at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital. The high occurrence of microcytic anaemia, primarily caused by a lack of iron, highlights the persistent issue of nutritional deficiencies in children [7]. The high occurrence of normocytic and macrocytic anaemia emphasises the diverse causes of anaemia in children, requiring a thorough diagnostic approach [8].

It is concerning to note that a significant portion of anaemic paediatric patients suffer from microcytic anaemia, which is primarily caused by iron deficiency [9]. This finding highlights the importance of addressing children's nutrition on a global scale. Anaemia in children can be caused by iron deficiency, which can significantly impact their cognitive and physical development [10]. The study's findings highlight the importance of addressing iron deficiency in a significant number of microcytic cases. This emphasises the need for greater attention to dietary interventions and

potentially implementing iron supplementation programs, particularly in areas where the prevalence rates are high [11,12]. It is worth noting that macrocytic anaemia was found in 15% of the study population, which is less common. This finding is particularly interesting because it is associated with deficiencies in vitamin B12 and folate [13]. This type of anaemia is frequently disregarded in children, yet it may suggest underlying problems with nutrient absorption or inadequate diet. This study highlights the importance of conducting comprehensive nutritional assessments in children diagnosed with macrocytic anaemia, as it reveals a significant link between vitamin B12 and folate deficiency and this type of anaemia [14,15].

There is a clear correlation between age and the type of anaemia, with noticeable trends. It appears that younger children are more susceptible to microcytic anaemia, which could be attributed to their increased need for iron during periods of rapid growth. On the other hand, older children and adolescents showed a higher prevalence of macrocytic and normocytic anaemia [16]. This

could be due to differences in their dietary habits or the development of other long-term health issues. Age-specific screening and management strategies for anaemia are crucial, as these findings highlight. Although the study offers valuable insights, it is important to note its limitations [17]. These limitations stem from its cross-sectional design, which prevents us from making any causal inferences between anaemia and its potential outcomes. In addition, the findings may have limited applicability due to the study being conducted in a single centre. Further investigation should prioritise longitudinal designs to monitor the progression of anaemia over time and how it reacts to various treatments. Multi-center studies could also provide valuable insights into regional variations in the epidemiology of paediatric anaemia [18].

The study emphasises the importance of regularly screening for anaemia in children. By utilising both clinicohematological and biochemical profiles, healthcare professionals can more effectively identify and address the different types and causes of anaemia [19]. Developing effective management strategies that are customised to address the root causes identified through comprehensive assessments is crucial for enhancing paediatric health outcomes on a global scale [20].

Conclusion

The study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital presents a detailed analysis of anaemia in children, focussing on its clinical, haematological, and biochemical aspects. The findings highlight a significant occurrence of microcytic anaemia, primarily caused by a lack of iron. Additionally, it emphasises the occurrence of macrocytic anaemia linked to deficiencies in vitamin B12 and folate, especially in older children and adolescents. These findings highlight the significance of focused screening and intervention approaches, customised to tackle particular nutritional deficiencies and types of anaemia. The findings strongly support the inclusion of regular anaemia screening in paediatric healthcare protocols. This will help identify and address anaemia at an early stage, with the ultimate goal of minimising its impact on child health and development.

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